

Synthesis, Magnetic and Spectral Studies of some Schiff Base Chelates of Iron-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II)

G. L. CHOUDHARY*, S. R. PRASAD and A. RAHMAN

Research Laboratories, P. G. Department of Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj-816 109

Manuscript received 27 April 1994, revised 6 May 1996, accepted 9 August 1996

The Schiff base ligands form complexes with divalent metal ions of different stoichiometries. The Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are six-coordinated with an octahedral or distorted octahedral geometry and the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are four-coordinated with a tetrahedral geometry around the metal ions. Metal chlorides are more toxic in comparison to their respective complexes and ligands.

Ligands having quinazoline-4(3*H*)-one show a variety of biological activities¹. These compounds are important for their donor properties and their use in chemotherapy. Here we report synthesis of two Schiff bases of substituted-quinazoline-4(3*H*)-ones, viz. 3-amino-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazoline-3',4'-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (AMQDMB) and 3-amino-2-phenyl-4(3*H*)-quinazoline-3',4'-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (APQDMB) and their complexes with Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} . Toxicological effect of the ligands and complexes have also been studied.

The title ligands have the following general structure :

X = CH_3 ($L' = \text{AMQDMB}$) or C_2H_5 ($L'' = \text{APQDMB}$)

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable in air and non-hygroscopic. They are soluble in DMF but insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The analytical and physical data indicate their compositions as $[\text{M}L_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{M}'L_2\text{Cl}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} ; $\text{M}' = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $L = L'/L''$. The molar conductance (in DMF at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) values of the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes (Table 1) indicate them as 1 : 2 electrolyte², and that of the complexes of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} indicate their non-electrolytic nature³.

Magnetic data and visible spectra : The μ_{eff} values of the Fe^{II} complexes (4.90–5.15 B.M.) are in good agreement with the reported value of high-spin octahedral⁴ Fe^{II} complexes. Electronic spectral bands at 10 450–10 550, 31 400–31 550 and 40 500–40 600 cm^{-1} , are attributed to ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^5E_g(D)$, ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(H)$ and ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^3E_g(H)$ transitions respectively. These transitions are spin-forbidden and are possibly due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the ligand or due to merger of both the transitions. The Dq value (1 050 cm^{-1}) is very close to that for octahedral Fe^{II} complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)		Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	N		
$\text{Fe}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	7.18 (7.22)	10.82 (10.87)	15.1	4.90
$\text{Fe}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	6.17 (6.20)	9.33 (9.37)	16.2	5.15
$\text{Co}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	7.53 (7.59)	10.75 (10.81)	18.0	4.62
$\text{Co}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	6.50 (6.55)	9.28 (9.33)	18.3	4.72
$\text{Ni}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	7.51 (7.57)	10.80 (10.83)	18.8	3.10
$\text{Ni}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	6.47 (6.52)	9.31 (9.35)	19.0	3.20
$\text{Zn}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	8.30 (8.36)	10.66 (10.73)	120.1	Diamag.
$\text{Zn}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	7.18 (7.21)	9.23 (9.27)	124.7	Diamag.
$\text{Cd}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	13.50	10.10	130.2	Diamag.
$\text{Cd}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	11.76 (11.79)	8.75 (8.81)	133.6	Diamag.
$\text{Hg}L_2\text{Cl}_2$	21.80 (21.86)	9.10 (9.15)	160	Diamag.
$\text{Hg}L'_2\text{Cl}_2$	19.22 (19.26)	8.00 (8.06)	159.1	Diamag.

* $L' = \text{AMQDMB}$, $L'' = \text{APQDMB}$.

The magnetic moments for Co^{II} complexes (Table 1) are consistent with the reported value of high-spin octahedral geometry⁵ of Co^{II} complexes with orbital contribution. The electronic spectra of these complexes show three bands at 8 900–9 300, 18 700–19 000 and 22 800–23 400 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β values have been found to be 2.07, 0.90, 1 000 cm^{-1} and 0.98 respectively, which agree with the values for octahedral Co^{II} complexes⁶.

The magnetic moments for Ni^{II} complexes confirms the presence of two unpaired electrons and some orbital contribution due to mixing of excited state with lowest state⁷. It is in good agreement with the reported value of octahedral geometry of Ni^{II} complexes. The three bands characteristic of octahedral geometry are observed at 8 500–8 600, 14 200–14 300 and 25 100–25 250 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $(\nu_1) {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $(\nu_2) {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $(\nu_3) {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The values of ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β which are 1.70, 1.0, 890 cm^{-1} and 0.89 respectively, are in good agreement with the octahedral geometry for these complexes⁸.

On the basis of elemental analysis, conductance, ir and ^1H nmr spectral data, tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes⁹.

Infrared spectra : In the ir spectra of the ligands $-\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch, $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretch, $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bending vibrations were at the expected values¹⁰. The ligand bands at 1 610 (L') and 1 620 cm^{-1} (L'') (azomethine stretch) shifted by 15–25 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates, indicating the coordination through azomethine nitrogen¹¹. The ligand bands at 1 670 (L') and 1 690 cm^{-1} (L'') ($-\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch), underwent lowering by 50 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates, indicating coordination through amido oxygen¹². The coordination through azomethine nitrogen and amido oxygen were further confirmed by $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ bands at 550–620 and 475–535 cm^{-1} respectively¹³.

The bands of weak intensity at 270–275 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$. The band of very strong intensity at 1 265 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be assigned to ν_{Co} ¹⁴. The position and other characteristics of this band are retained in all the complexes. This indicates that the oxygen atoms of the methoxy groups do not take part in coordination.

^1H nmr spectra : The OCH_3 protons in the free ligand revealed a sharp singlet at δ 3.80. In the spectra of all the complexes it remained in the same position which confirms that the oxygen atoms of the OCH_3 groups do not take part in coordination. All the ligands and complexes showed signals at δ 2.4 (s, CH_3) and (m, ArH)¹⁵. The azomethine proton suffering deshielding appeared at δ 8.4–7.8 in all the complexes, indicating coordination through the nitrogen of the azomethine group to the metal ion¹⁶.

Biological activity : The toxic effects of the complexes, ligands and metal chlorides were studied on growth of a green alga *Chorella*. It was found that the metal chlorides are more toxic than their respective complexes and ligands. The order of toxicity of ligands were observed as : AMQDMB > APQDMB. The less toxic nature of the ligands may be due to the presence of substituted groups in the quinazolone ring.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents (B.D.H.) were purified by standard methods.

3-Amino-2-methylquinazoline-4(3*H*)-ones and 3-amino-2-phenylquinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones were prepared by the reported methods¹⁷. The ligands L' and L'' were prepared by refluxing a mixture of ethanolic solutions of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and the respective substituted-quinazoline-4(3*H*)-ones (1 : 1 molar ratio) on a water-bath for about 6 h and then cooled. The resulting solids were washed, crystallised from DMF and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 : AMQDMB, m.p. 130°, APQDMB, 159°.

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solutions of the metal chloride (0.005 mol) with the ligands (0.01 mol) for 7–8 h on a water-bath. A pH 7–8 was maintained in all cases. The resulting complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 (m.p.s. of all the complexes were above 250°).

C, N and H were determined microanalytically at I.I.T., Kanpur. Metals and chlorine were estimated by standard procedures¹⁸. Magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was measured by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. Molar conductance was measured using a Systronics 303 conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20-A spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Perkin-Elmer 400A spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Kanpur and ^1H nmr spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on an EM 930 spectrometer at R.S.I.C., Madras.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their indebtedness to Dr. T. Sharma, Head, University Department of Chemistry, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, for his interest, encouragement and discussions and thank Dr. U. N. Mishra, Head, Botany Department, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, for toxicological studies.

References

- M. L. GUJRAL, P.N. SAXENA and R.S. TEWARI, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1955, **43**, 637; G.D. LAUBACH and M.M. MCLAMORE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, **55**, 25998; R. K. SAXENA and M. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 443.
- W. J. GEASY, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
- Y. M. PATEL and J. R. SHAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 800.
- M. CIAMPOLINI, *Struc. Bonding*, 1969, **6**, 52.
- A. C. RANDE and V. V. SUBHA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 42.
- A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
- F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, p. 894.
- G. RUELINS and W. MANCH, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1960, **193**; MINCHAEAL and R. A. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 71
- B. N. KESHRI and L. K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 883.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules"; 2nd ed., Methuen, London, 1958.

CHOU DHARY, PRASAD & RAHMAN : SYNTHESIS, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL STUDIES OF SOME SCHIFF BASE *etc.*

11. P. R. SHUKLA, A. M. JAISWAL and G. NARIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 29.
12. K. L. REDDY, S. SRIHARI and P. LINGAIH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1020.
13. N. SONODA and T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1975, **21**, 261; K. NAKAMOTO and S. L. MCGARTHY, "Spectroscopy and Structure of Metal Chelate Compounds", Wiley, London, 1968.
14. A. N. SUNDER RAM, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Kerala, 1977.
15. M. N. MOOKHERJEE, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 388.
16. N. K. SHARMA, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1950, **42**, 463.
17. L. LEGRAND and N. LOZACH, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1961, 1400.
18. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1981.